

LEARNING TO SPEAK AND WRITE IN RUSSIAN LESSONS

Rasulova Matluba Hamzayevna- associate professor,
candidate of philological sciences of the Kokand State
Pedagogical Institute

Rakhimova Gulnozakhon Vakhobjon kizi-student of the
direction “Native language and literature (Russian language and
literature)” of the Kokand State Pedagogical Institute

***Annotation.** Speaking, as a productive type of speech activity, is a way of expressing the speaker's own thoughts, represents a creative process - the creation (production) of a new speech statement. Reproduction of the finished text (retelling) is not speaking in the true sense of the word, being only a preparation for speaking.*

***Key words:** educational system, speaking, active component, verbal communication, psychological characteristics, work on teaching speaking, teaching dialogic speech, teaching monologue speech.*

***Аннотация.** Говорение, как продуктивный вид речевой деятельности, является способом выражения собственных мыслей говорящего, представляет творческий процесс – создание нового речевого высказывания. Воспроизведение готового текста (пересказ) не является говорением в подлинном смысле этого слова, являясь лишь подготовкой к говорению. В статье рассматриваются некоторые аспекты говорения, как способ выражения собственных мыслей говорящего.*

***Ключевые слова:** образовательная система, говорение, активный компонент, речевое общение, психологическая характеристика, работы по обучению говорению, обучение диалогической речи, обучение монологической речи.*

Speaking, as a productive type of speech activity, is a way of expressing the speaker's own thoughts, represents a creative process - the creation (production) of a new speech statement. Reproduction of the finished text (retelling) is not speaking in the true sense of the word, being only a preparation for speaking.

Unfortunately, teaching speaking in Russian language lessons often comes down to retelling dialogues and monologues, no attention is paid to the development of unprepared speech, no conditions are created for motivating actions (the intention to ask, the desire to report something). Thus, teaching speaking will be most effective if teaching speaking is based on creative exercises aimed at creating a new speech product.

Speaking as a type of speech activity is possible only when the speaker owns the language material necessary for utterance (knows words, grammatical forms, correctly articulates sounds, etc.).

Therefore, the work of teaching speaking should provide for the assimilation language tools and automation of language skills.

To develop an effective methodology for teaching speaking in a non-native language, it is necessary to distinguish between prepared and unprepared speaking. Prepared speaking is characterized by the fact that both content and language design are prepared in advance. A statement prepared on the basis of a ready-made sample: memorization, retelling - creates the necessary language base for unprepared speaking. Unprepared speaking differs from prepared speaking by focusing on the semantic content of the statement, the absence of a given language material and a given content: the content of the statement is dictated by speech situations, the selection of language means and the construction of speech occur simultaneously at the moment of speaking.

A prepared speech is more often a reproductive speech, a reproduction of a finished, someone else's speech, while an unprepared speech is always creative, productive. Unprepared speech is an indicator of the degree of language proficiency; accordingly, work on the development of unprepared speech skills should prevail in the educational process.

Speaking as a component of oral speech communication is realized in two forms of oral speech - dialogical and monologue, therefore the content of teaching speaking involves teaching dialogue and monologue.

The question of what to give preference to in teaching speaking - a dialogue or a monologue, is solved ambiguously in the methodological literature.

For example, A.A. Gerdt believes that learning a dialogic form of communication "develops ... oral speech skills much faster." A.A. Leontiev, on the contrary, claims that "it is monologue speech that requires special training. In our opinion, the preferred teaching of only one of the forms of oral speech is illegal, because. in natural speech communication, both forms of speech are equally widely used.

Thus, the work of teaching speaking should include the inculcation of skills for creating various types of prepared and unprepared statements, work on teaching both dialogue and monologue. Dialogical speech, according to V.V. Vinogradov, is "the most common form of social and verbal communication", therefore it is advisable to start teaching oral speech at school with this particular form.

In teaching dialogic speech, it is necessary to take into account its characteristic features, specific structural and linguistic features. For the methodology of teaching dialogic speech, it is important to define the concept of "dialogue".

In the linguistic and methodological literature it is unambiguously stated that the basic unit of dialogue is dialogic unity, in which not one replica, but a combination of replicas that form this unity, serves as an exponent of the semantic meaning of an utterance.

From this it naturally follows that the linguistic basis for teaching dialogic speech should not be separate phrases-replicas, but dialogic units. In order to instill in students the skills and abilities to conduct a dialogue in various areas of communication, it is necessary to organize speech training on such types of dialogue as:

- 1) situational dialogue (dialogue-questioning, dialogue-message, dialogue-motivation);
- 2) dialogue-conversation (thematic conversation);
- 3) dialogue-discussion.

The formation of skills and abilities to conduct a dialogue occurs with the help of special exercises that can be combined into two groups:

- 1) preparatory exercises, the purpose of which is the accumulation of ready-made speech material in memory, the formation of skills for the design of stimulating and responsive replicas;
- 2) 2) speech exercises, the purpose of which is to develop the ability to operate with the accumulated speech and language material to express one's own thoughts in unprepared dialogic speech.
- 3) Preparatory exercises include the following types of tasks:
- 4) - familiarization of students with samples of ready-made dialogues (reading, memorization);
- 5) - reproduction of a ready-made dialogue - repetition of remarks after a teacher or an announcer;
- 6) - variation of these dialogues: the choice of the proposed several options for replicas of the most suitable for a given situation; selection for a given cue-stimulus of a cue-reaction that is suitable in meaning;
- 7) replacement in the dialogue of one or more replicas; deployment of replicas, etc.;
- continuation of dialogues;
- compiling new dialogues by imitating these patterns.

Speech exercises include the following tasks:

- drawing up dialogues according to the content of the texts read;
- drawing up dialogues on the content of illustrative clarity: drawings, paintings, slides, filmstrips, etc.;
- drawing up dialogues on verbal situations (situation described verbally). More often these are imaginary situations, for example: "Meeting friends after the holidays", "After the performance", "In the library", etc.
- composing dialogues on given topics. These are thematic conversations, which require knowledge of the subject of speech;

- participation in dialogues-discussions, starting from the 7th grade. As you can see, the teaching of dialogical speech represents a certain system, including work on different types of dialogue based on special exercises - preparatory and speech.

4. Dialogue and monologue represent two forms of the same process - speaking, so the training of dialogic and monologue speech must be organized in parallel.

Oral monologue speech in the process of mastering it by students is characterized by: a) discontinuity, which manifests itself in stops, in the repetition of individual words, syllables, sounds;

b) intonation inseparability of speech, i.e. pronunciation of separate verbal groups without the necessary intonational delimitation of them from each other;

c) the lack of intonation of the whole text, which is usually associated with the absence of a specific intent of the statement;

d) intonation monotone.

The skills of monologue speech do not come by themselves, they need to be specially developed. Special training in monologue utterance involves familiarity with speech concepts: text, topic, main idea of the utterance, means of communication, etc.

The basis for constructing a monologue statement is the ability to: 1) build a statement in accordance with the logic of the development of thought; 2) the ability to construct sentences and link them together. These skills are formed in the process of teaching monologue speech when performing the following types of work:

- retelling is one of the most common tasks in the practice of teaching monologue speech. Distinguish between verbatim retelling and retelling in your own words. Retelling as a methodical device is mainly focused on the amount of memory. Better perception of the text and its reproduction is facilitated by working with the plan.

- an oral story based on what they saw, heard, experienced and the creative imagination of students is very effective in developing the skills of monologue speech. The stories are accompanied by assignments for describing objects (trees, houses), nature, interiors, etc.

Information, report - these are monologues with elements of official business and journalistic style.

Message, report - performances of students, thematically related to the subjects studied at school. These statements are characterized by the features of a monologue of the oral form of the scientific (popular science) language.

So, the considered features of the formation of students' oral speech, the listed exercises aimed at developing the dialogic and monologue speech of students, contribute to the successful formation of the communicative skills of schoolchildren.

Literature:

1. Belova, TG The use of health-preserving technologies in order to increase the efficiency of work to preserve and strengthen the health of children / TG Belova // Collection of materials of the Annual International Scientific and Practical Conference "Education and Training of Young Children". - 2016. - No. 5.
2. Ivanova, LA, Kazakova, OA, Jerusalemova, MV Formation of motor activity in preschool children through new health-forming technologies / LA Ivanova et al. // Concept. - 2014. - No. 12.
3. Melekhina, N. A., Kolmykova, L. A. Non-traditional approaches to the physical education of children in preschool educational institutions / N. A. Melekhina, L. A. Kolmykova. - M.: Childhood-Press, 2012. -- 112 p.
4. Sharipova, D. D., Shakhmurova, G. A., Tairova, M. P. The introduction of health-saving technologies in the educational process of preschoolers / D. D. Sharipova et al. // Collection of materials of the Annual International Scientific and Practical Conference "Education and early childhood education". - 2016. - No. 5.
5. Shchekina, NB Prerequisites for the development of ideas about health and a healthy lifestyle / NB Shchekina // Pedagogy, psychology and medico-biological problems of physical education and sports. - 2012. - No. 1. - P. 125–128.
6. Yakimova, EA Strengthening the health of the child in kindergarten: a methodological guide / EA Yakimova. - M.: Karo, 2014. -- 296 p.
7. Yakovleva, LV Physical development and health of children 3–7 years old / LV Yakovleva. - M.: Vlados, 2014. -- 315 p.